

TRAINING OF BUS DRIVERS: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract: This thesis analyzes the system of training, retraining and advanced training of drivers of category «D» in the country, as well as corresponding regulations. On the basis of proposals on improvement of procedure for training, retraining and advanced training of drivers of category «D» are elaborated.

Key words: training of drivers, retraining, advanced training, traffic accidents, speed, traffic signs and lanes, directional vehicle.

Аннотация: ушбу тезисда республикамизда «Д» тоифали ҳайдовчиларни тайёрлаш, қайта тайёрлаш ва малакасини ошириш тизими ҳамда унга оид норматив-ҳуқуқий ҳужжатлар таҳлил қилинган. Шу асосида «Д» тоифали ҳайдовчиларини тайёрлаш, қайта тайёрлаш ва малакасини ошириш тартибини такомиллаштириш юзасидан таклифлар билдирилган.

Калит сўзлар: ҳайдовчиларни тайёрлаш, қайта тайёрлаш, малакасини ошириш, йўл-транспорт ҳодисалари, ҳаракатланиш тезлиги, йўл белги ва чизиқлари, йўналишли транспорт воситаси.

Аннотация: в тезисе проведен анализ системы подготовки, переподготовки и повышения квалификаций водителей категории «Д» в нашей республике, а также соответствующие нормативные акты. На основании этих данных, разработаны рекомендации по совершенствованию порядка подготовки, переподготовки и повышения квалификаций водителей категории «Д».

Ключевые слова: подготовка водителей, переподготовка, повышение квалификаций, дорожно-транспортные происшествия, скорость движения, дорожные знаки и разметки, маршрутные транспортные средства.

Ensuring the safety of road users is one of the important tasks of the state. After all, this is a component of ensuring the safety of citizens. Large-scale measures in this direction are being carried out in our country. In particular, the regulatory framework of the industry is being improved, specific mechanisms for training, retraining and upgrading the skills of drivers are being implemented.

Approved by the decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 408 of May 31, 2018 "On measures to further improve the licensing procedure for the provision of non-state educational services for the training, retraining and upgrading of drivers of motor vehicles and urban electric vehicles" Institutions and other legal entities engaged in non-governmental educational services for the training, retraining and upgrading of drivers of motor vehicles and urban electric vehicles, as well as registration of educational groups, as well as the procedure for conducting exams and issuing a national driver's license" a system of training, retraining and improving their qualifications is implemented.

This Regulation regulates the registration of training groups of state educational institutions and other legal entities engaged in the provision of non-state educational services for the training, retraining and upgrading of the drivers of motor vehicles and city electric vehicles, the State Road Safety Service and its regional divisions of motor vehicles and determines the procedure for conducting examinations for granting the right to drive city electric vehicles and issuing a national driver's license.

All motor vehicles are divided into "A", "V", "S", "D", "VE", "SE" and "DE" categories, as well as trams and trolleybuses, according to their type, function and management characteristics. In the corresponding position of the driver's license issued for driving them, the date and period of permission to drive a vehicle of this category are indicated.

According to the regulation, it is stipulated to obtain the opinion of the General Directorate of Road Traffic Safety of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan before the state educational institutions start their activities on the provision of training and retraining services for drivers of motor vehicles and urban electric vehicles. It is stated that state educational institutions apply to the General Directorate of Road Safety through the higher state office in the prescribed manner.

Training groups of a legal entity providing non-state educational services for training and retraining drivers of motor vehicles and urban electric vehicles. on the basis of the license issued for the provision of educational services, according to the instructions of the General Directorate of Road Traffic Safety, it is determined to be registered by the regional Road Traffic Safety Departments.

After the heads of educational organizations have agreed with the regional Traffic Safety Department on the start and end dates of training in driver training and retraining training groups, they must register the group list in the secretariat of the regional Traffic Safety Department within 10 days in the prescribed manner.

The number of candidates in the training and retraining groups of drivers of motor vehicles and urban electric vehicles should not exceed 25 people.

To obtain a national driver's license, citizens take exams at their permanent or temporary residences, and military servicemen at their places of service, at the registration and examination units of the regional Traffic Safety Department.

National driver's licenses for driving motor vehicles of categories "A", "V", "S" and "D" and trams and trolleybuses are issued to persons who have passed theoretical and practical exams at the registration and examination departments of the regional Traffic Safety Department.

In the retraining of drivers of category "C" from persons who have the right to drive motor vehicles of category "B" and (or) "D", category "D" from persons who have the right to drive motor vehicles of category "B" and (or) "C" theoretical and practical exams are given in the retraining of motor vehicle drivers. Only practical exams are given in the retraining of motor vehicle drivers of categories "BE", "CE" and "DE".

A person, if he has driven a motor vehicle for at least three years, is allowed to retrain and pass exams to category "D".

At the end of the training period, 16 years old to get the right to drive a class "A" motor vehicle, 18 years old to get the right to drive class "V" and/or "S" motor vehicles, the right to drive class "D" motor vehicles, trams and trolleybuses It is established that persons who have reached the age of 21 will be allowed to take exams at the registration and examination units of the regional Traffic Safety Department.

Also, persons who have the right to drive public vehicles are required to have a driver's license that gives them the right to drive motor vehicles of category "D" and "DE". In this:

"D" - motor vehicles intended for passenger transportation, with more than eight seats except the driver's seat, motor vehicles of category "D" with the permissible total weight of the trailer not exceeding 750 kg;

"DE" includes motor vehicles of category "D" and articulated buses with a permissible total weight of the trailer over 750 kg.

Drivers who express their desire to carry out passenger transportation activities in urban, suburban, intercity, international routes in legal entities within the specified period and directions (for drivers with driving experience in "D" category vehicles - 60 hours, for drivers without driving experience - 224 hours) are allowed to independently drive vehicles of the appropriate category only after passing practical driving skills (internship).

In this case, the drivers of all motor vehicles shall serve passengers on a commercial basis within the period determined by the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

and it is emphasized that the drivers who engage in it must undergo a mandatory medical examination once a year.

It is regrettable that, despite the above requirements for the training of drivers of "D" category vehicles, traffic accidents involving bus drivers are taking place.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the material and technical base of the educational institutions engaged in the training, retraining and improvement of the skills of drivers in our country should be re-examined, the professors who conduct the training should be highly educated in the field, the quality of the training should be strictly controlled, the training of drivers in the educational institutions, retraining It is proposed to establish an Association with a unified policy on training and professional development.

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